

NON-DESTRUCTIVE TESTING OF DEFECTS IN THICK COMPOSITES BY MEANS OF PULSE AND LOCK-IN THERMOGRAPHY TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on non-destructive inspection of defects within thick (20 mm) glass and carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy (GFRP and CFRP) composites by means of pulse and lock-in thermography methods in order to evaluate the detection limits as a function of depth. Composite panels with back-face drilled holes and composite plugs were designed and manufactured in order to represent voids, delaminations and kissing de-bond defects. A commercially available pulse thermography system was used and a lock-in experimental setup was developed by the authors. A COMSOL active thermography model was developed to simulate the transient temperature distribution during the experiments, using the measured material properties and geometry as inputs. The heat flux boundary condition was calculated in MATLAB by considering the geometric spreading of the lamp beams. This paper presents the results of experiments carried out to assess the effectiveness and detection capabilities of pulse and lock-in active thermography techniques for inspecting thick composite laminates.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is a growing interest in the applications of pulse [1] and lock-in [2] active thermography techniques for the detection of defects in composite structures. These methods use either an external heating or cooling source to stimulate a temperature change in the material. As the heat conducts through the material, time dependent changes in the measured thermography signal can be used to indicate the presence and location of defects. It is also possible to relate the time dependent behavior to the depth of the defect [3]. Although these two techniques are distinctly different, they are used for very similar component/structure inspection applications [1]. The choice of the most appropriate technique, pulse or lock-in, mainly depends on the specific application with particular regard to the properties of the materials involved and the specific requirements of the quality control process [4]. There have been no defined standards or procedures for the application of these techniques on composite materials. The most relevant standard is ASTM E2582 [5], which is based on infrared flash thermography for the detection of sub-surface defects for aerospace applications.

Researchers have investigated the defect detection capabilities and limits of pulse [4, 6-9] and lock-in [1, 2, 4, 10-17] thermography methods on GFRP and CFRP composite panels, ranging in thickness from 3 mm to 12.5 mm, containing near sub-surface natural or artificial defects. The deepest detectable defects reported are 7.5 mm and 6 mm in 9 mm [10] and 12.5 mm [11] thick GFRP composite panels, respectively. Maldague [3] and Meola et al [6] reported the importance of the defect diameter versus the thickness of the sample. Maldague [3] found a flaw detection limit for homogeneous isotropic materials for which the radius of the smallest detectable defect should be at least one to two times larger than its sub-surface depth. The sensitivity decreased linearly with depth for orthotropic CFRP materials.

In this study, quasi-isotropic GFRP and CFRP composite reference defect panels (thickness of 20 mm) with back-face drilled holes of various diameters and depths were designed and manufactured. The drilled holes (diameters: 2 – 20 mm and depths: 2 – 19.75 mm) were machined to represent voids and delaminations. In addition, composite plugs for the 20 mm diameter holes were machined (interference fit) from the same material as the parent laminate in order to create a more accurate representation of a void cavity and delamination/kissing de-bond. A ThermoScope pulse thermography kit and a lock-in thermography system developed by the authors were used. A COMSOL model was developed to simulate the transient temperature distribution during the thermography experiments, using the measured material properties and geometry as inputs. The heat flux boundary condition was calculated by considering the geometric spreading of the lamp beams. Several thermal material properties were measured that were required for the inspection experiments and modelling. This study discusses the effectiveness of both the lock-in and pulse thermography inspection techniques for thick GFRP and CFRP composites, and their capabilities in terms of defect detection.

2 THEORY

2.1 Pulse Thermography Technique

Pulse thermography inspection is based on short duration exposure (of the order of a few milliseconds) under high power light sources to heat the sample. This generates a transient heat flow that propagates from the sample surface through the thickness of the material. Defects within the sample modify the heat conduction to varying extents depending on the nature of the defect, and thus altering the surface cooling rate compared to that occurring over non-defective regions. This results in a surface temperature contrast over the defective area, which can be measured using an infrared (IR) camera. The location, shape and size of the defects can be predicted from the recorded thermal image sequence. Defects located deeper below the surface are revealed later in time, with a consequent reduction in temperature contrast. These dependences can be approximated as follows:

$$t \sim h^2/\alpha \text{ and } c \sim 1/h^3 \quad (1)$$

where t is the time, h is the depth, c is the temperature contrast and α is the thermal diffusivity [3].

2.2 Lock-in Thermography Technique

In the lock-in technique, the sample is heated periodically by means of halogen lamps. An IR camera is used to record the oscillating surface temperature of the inspected object by taking a series of images. The image recording is synchronized with the modulation frequency and the camera takes four images within one cycle.

The lock-in system obtains four signal values (S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4) for every pixel in the image. The indices refer to the recording time. From these values, the system calculates a phase value $\phi(x, y)$. It then produces a phase image by using the ϕ values (Equation 2). The captured images are processed using Equation 3 to calculate amplitude (A). In comparison to the thermal image, the phase image provides more contrast changes at defect locations and it is less sensitive to non-uniform surface emission and ambient disturbance [19].

$$\phi = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{S_1 - S_3}{S_2 - S_4} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$A = \sqrt{(S_1 - S_3)^2 + (S_2 - S_4)^2} \quad (3)$$

The following equation is used in order to calculate the thermal diffusion length [14]:

$$\mu = \sqrt{(2k)/(\omega\rho c)} = \sqrt{\alpha/(\pi f)} \quad (4)$$

where α is the thermal diffusivity of the material, f is the wave frequency, ρ is the density, c is the specific heat, k is the thermal conductivity and ω is the angular modulation frequency of the heat source. The depth range, for the amplitude image, is given by μ . The maximum depth that can be inspected for the phase image corresponds to [14]:

$$h_{max} = 1.8\mu \quad (5)$$

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Reference Panel Design

GFRP ($[+45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ]_{16s}$) and CFRP ($[+45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ]_{8s}$) reference panels (17 cm \times 30 cm \times 2 cm thick) fabricated from HexPly 913 and SE 84LV epoxy prepreg systems, respectively were autoclave processed. Flat bottom holes were then drilled from one face to obtain cylindrical holes with varying diameters (2 mm to 20 mm) and depths (aspect ratios, diameter to depth, from 0.5 to 10). The holes were sized and spaced based on guidance given in ASTM E2582 for infrared flash thermographic inspection of composite panels and repair patches used in aerospace applications [5] and NASA's requirements for ultrasonic inspection [18]. Whilst these are not specifically for pulse and lock-in thermography techniques, the preparation procedures are useful guides for manufacturing reference defect artefacts (Figure 1). The reason for having a wide range of back-face drilled hole sizes and depths was to establish the detection limitations of the methods.

Figure 1: Illustration of composite reference panels with back-face drilled holes

The measured material properties are presented in Table 1. For the emissivity measurements, one sample (50 mm \times 50 mm) from each panel was tested using an absolute hemispherical reflectometer and a Fourier transform spectrometer. Independent measurements from different areas of the surface were made on each sample. Specific heat capacity measurements were undertaken by DSC using disc geometry specimens of 4.8 mm diameter and 0.5 mm thickness. Thermal conductivity measurements were undertaken by Modulated Temperature DSC using the specific heat capacity values and additional measurements using cylindrical specimens (diameter of 4.8 mm and thickness of 3.5 mm).

Round samples (diameter of 12.4 mm, thickness of 3 mm) were machined for the diffusivity and measured using flash thermography. These three thermal property measurements were undertaken using specimens machined from the top, middle and bottom sections of the panels in order to get more representative average values. Fibre volume fraction and density measurements were based on burn-off for GFRP and acid digestion for CFRP using 20 mm × 20 mm samples. Porosity measurements showed that the level of porosity in the samples was close to 0%.

Table 1: Material properties

	Emissivity	Thermal Conductivity (W/K m)	Specific heat capacity J/(gK)	Diffusivity ($\text{m}^2/\text{s} \times 10^{-6}$)	Fibre volume fraction (%)	Density (g/ml)
CFRP	0.93 ± 0.01	0.54 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.03	0.40 ± 0.002	54.4 ± 0.1	1.55 ± 0.003
GFRP	0.96 ± 0.01	0.49 ± 0.01	0.91 ± 0.03	0.26 ± 0.002	55.5 ± 0.2	1.97 ± 0.003

3.2 Pulse Thermography Experimental Procedure

A ThermoScope pulse thermography system with 2kJ total output rating with a flash duration of 5 ms supplied by LOT-Oriel Ltd (Figure 2) was used. The regions indicated by red hatched lines shown in Figure 1a were inspected under the flash hood. After the flash, the thermal camera monitored the temperature changes for 30 seconds at 50 Hz frequency on the front face of the samples. The images from 1st and 2nd derivative of heat amplitude clearly showed the defects.

Figure 2: Illustration of pulse thermography experimental setup

3.3 Lock-in Thermography Experimental Procedure

The lock-in experimental setup used in this study is schematically shown in Figure 3. The system consisted of four 1kW halogen lamps, an amplifier, a function generator, a FLIR infrared camera and Altair LI software. In the literature, there has been no defined procedure for determining the relationship between the frequency, distance between the sample and the heat source, number of lamps and power of lamps for the lock-in thermography. In this study, an experimental procedure was developed for the detection of defects in 20 mm thick GFRP and CFRP composite panels.

Due to the thicknesses of the GFRP and CFRP specimens and the diffusivities presented in Table 1, the sinusoidal experimental times were calculated as ~55 minutes ($f = 0.0003\text{Hz}$) and ~83 minutes ($f = 0.0002\text{Hz}$), respectively. In order not to overheat the samples, a reasonable minimum frequency of 0.001Hz (~16 minutes) was selected and the lamps were focused at the centre of each sample and at the closest possible distance. The experiments were conducted in transmission (Figure 3) mode with four halogen lamps in order to obtain i) faster and homogenous heat flow within the sample; and ii) better and clearer temperature difference on the front surface.

Figure 3: Illustration of lock-in thermography inspection setup

4 MODELLING STRATEGY

A 3D transient heat transfer model was developed using COMSOL finite element analysis software. The model consisted of the sample geometry with defects, material properties (Table 1), surface heat flux due to the lamps and convective heat flux boundary conditions from all external faces. The average element size used in the model was 7.5 mm, but smaller elements were used in regions where it was necessary to capture the geometric details. Approximately 250,000 second-order elements were used. The convective boundary conditions used an ambient temperature of 20°C and a heat transfer coefficient of 4 W m^{-2} , which was calculated by considering the heat flux and the temperature difference between the surface and the surrounding area. The sample was assumed to be at a uniform temperature of 20°C before the lamps were turned on. The surface heat fluxes were defined by creating a heat flux condition for each lamp and defining each condition to be spatially varying with a value of P/A (P : power emitted by the lamp, A : the area of the intersection of the light beam with the sample) within the ellipse calculated by a MATLAB code, and 0 outside of that ellipse. The transient behaviour of the lamps was implemented by multiplying the spatial variation by either $(1 + \sin[2 \pi f t])$, where f is the frequency of the lamp and t is time, for a sinusoidal variation in power, or by a function that takes the value 1 if $t < t_p$, where t_p is the pulse duration, and 0 otherwise for a pulse variation in power.

Initial results showed that defining the heat flux as P/A gave unrealistic temperature rises within the sample. These results suggested that the assumption that all of the light is absorbed by the sample and converted to thermal energy is unreasonable, but the appropriate model for absorption of light and conversion to heat was unknown. The heat fluxes were therefore adjusted by a scaling factor, constant for each model, such that the maximum temperature rises were approximately 20°C as this corresponds with the level of temperature change measured experimentally. The use of these scaling factors means that the temperature values are not quantitatively meaningful, and that plots obtained using different lamp arrangements cannot have temperature values compared. However, the qualitative patterns obtained from the models are directly comparable and can be compared to experimental results because it is expected that the unknown absorption factor will be constant and uniform for a given material over the temperature range seen experimentally.

5 RESULTS

The pulse thermography experimental (1st and 2nd derivatives of heat amplitude) and numerical results for the CFRP and GFRP panels are presented in Figure 4 and Figure 5, respectively. The kissing de-

bonds, which were represented by the full insertion of the composite plugs into 20 mm holes, were not detectable, and the 2nd derivative of defect A1 (see Figure 1b) (diameter of 20 mm and thickness of 18 mm) was barely noticeable (Figure 7). Table 2 shows the diameters and thicknesses of the detectable defects. For 20, 8, 6 and 5 mm diameter defects, the smallest detectable defect depth (h_2) was 16 mm that was 4 mm below the surface. h_2 was 19 mm for the 2 mm and 4 mm diameter defects for CFRP, whereas it was 18 mm for GFRP. The GFRP and CFRP inspection results were similar apart from 2 mm and 4 mm diameter defects with 18 mm depth that were only detectable for the GFRP sample.

For the lock-in thermography inspection results, the experimental and numerical results were similar (Figure 8a and 8b). Regardless of their depth, 2 mm diameter defects were not detectable. The defects in Group 4 (marked in Figure 1a) were barely detectable apart from $\text{Ø}8 \times 12$, $\text{Ø}6 \times 12$ and $\text{Ø}5 \times 12$ defects. In addition, the lock-in technique was not able to detect the kissing de-bond defects.

Table 2: Detectable defects by pulse thermography technique (d: diameter, h_2 : defect depth)

CFRP			GFRP		
d	h_2	d/ h_2	d	h_2	d/ h_2
20	18	1.11	20	18	1.11
20	16	1.25	20	16	1.25
8	19.5	0.41	8	19.5	0.41
8	19	0.42	8	19	0.42
8	18	0.44	8	18	0.44
8	17	0.47	8	17	0.47
8	16	0.50	8	16	0.50
6	19.5	0.31	6	19.5	0.31
6	19	0.32	6	19	0.32
6	18	0.33	6	18	0.33
6	17	0.35	6	17	0.35
6	16	0.38	6	16	0.38
5	19.5	0.26	5	19.5	0.26
5	19	0.26	5	19	0.26
5	18	0.28	5	18	0.28
5	17	0.29	5	17	0.29
5	16	0.31	5	16	0.31
4	19.75	0.20	4	19.75	0.20
4	19.5	0.21	4	19.5	0.21
4	19.25	0.21	4	19.25	0.21
4	19	0.21	4	19	0.21
			4	18	0.22
2	19.75	0.10	2	19.75	0.10
2	19.5	0.10	2	19.5	0.10
2	19.25	0.10	2	19.25	0.10
2	19	0.11	2	19	0.11
			2	18	0.11

Figure 4: CFRP pulse thermography inspection results

a) 1st Derivative

b) 2nd Derivative

c) Model

Figure 5: GFRP pulse thermography inspection results

CFRP GFRP
Figure 6: Summary of pulse thermography modelling results

a) 1st Derivative b) 2nd Derivative

Figure 7: Kissing de-bond inspection results

a) Group 1-5

b) Group 6, 7

Figure 8: Lock-in thermography results

6 CONCLUSION

This paper presents the results of experiments evaluating the defect detection capabilities and effectiveness of pulse and lock-in active thermography techniques for inspecting thick composite laminates. In order to assess the defect inspection capabilities of the techniques, relatively thick (20 mm) GFRP and CFRP composite panels containing various defects were designed and tested, unlike the thickness values reported in the literature.

The similarities between the modelling and experimental results demonstrated the potential of pulse and lock-in thermography modelling in aiding the future development and use of these non-destructive inspection techniques for composite structures.

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